

Scopus Search Techniques

Introduction: Scopus is a large, multidisciplinary database of abstracts and citations for peer-reviewed literature, including journals, books, and conference proceedings, developed by Elsevier. It covers a wide range of fields such as science, technology, medicine, social sciences, and arts and humanities.

Keep up-to-date and stay ahead of the competition with comprehensive coverage of academic journals, preprints, books, and conference proceedings, including over 25.2M+ open access documents.

- 100M+ records
- 30.2 active serial titles
- 404K+ books
- 2.6M+ preprints

Identify trends for key topics:

Scopus' literature search is built to distil massive amounts of information down to the most relevant documents and information in less time.

With Scopus, you can search and filter results in the following ways:

- **Document search:** Search directly from the homepage and use detailed search options to ensure you find the document(s) you want
- **Author search:** Search for a specific author by name or by Open Research and Contributor Identifier ID (ORCID)
- **Affiliation search:** Identify and assess an affiliation's scholarly output, collaborating institutions and top authors
- **Advanced search:** Narrow the scope of your search using field codes, proximity operators and/or Boolean operators
- **Refine results:** Scopus makes it easy to refine your results list to specific categories of documents
- **Language interface:** The Scopus interface is available in Chinese and Japanese; content is not localized, but you can switch the interface to one of these language options (and switch back to English, the default language) at the bottom of any Scopus page

Practical example of search techniques

1. Document search:

From the dropdown next to the box, select:
“Article title, Abstract, Keywords”

Enter Your Search Terms- In the search box

Year: 2018- present

The screenshot shows the Scopus search interface. At the top left is the Scopus logo. The main heading is "Start exploring". Below it are tabs for "Documents", "Authors", "Researcher Discovery", and "Organizations". The "Documents" tab is selected. There are three search input fields: "Search within" (set to "Article title, Abstract, Keywords"), "Search documents" (containing the query "automation" AND "library services"), "Published from" (set to "2018"), and "To" (set to "Present"). There is also a field for "Added to Scopus" set to "Anytime". At the bottom of the search area are buttons for "+ Add search field", "Remove date range", "Advanced document search", "Reset", and "Search".

➤ Result-

The screenshot shows the Scopus search results page. At the top left is the Scopus logo. The main heading is "99 documents found". Below it are tabs for "Documents", "Preprints", and "Secondary documents". The "Documents" tab is selected. There are buttons for "Save search", "Set search alert", "+ Add search field", "Reset", and "Search". The search query is "automation" AND "library services". The results are sorted by "Date (newest)". The first result is an article titled "Enhancing library services with artificial intelligence: A framework for an automated news delivery system" by Jhan, P.I., Sree Kumar, M.G., and Kurialose, R. The article is published in the IJIA Journal, 5(3) Special Issue: Artificial Intelligence (AI): Transforming Global Librarianship, pp. 836-848, in 2025. The article has 1 citation. There are buttons for "Show abstract", "View at Publisher", and "Related documents".

Document title	Authors	Source	Year	Citations
1 Enhancing library services with artificial intelligence: A framework for an automated news delivery system	Jhan, P.I., Sree Kumar, M.G., Kurialose, R.	IJIA Journal, 5(3) Special Issue: Artificial Intelligence (AI): Transforming Global Librarianship, pp. 836-848	2025	1

Now you can also filter/Refine it, by –

1. Range
2. Author name
3. Subject Area
4. Document Type
5. Source title
6. Keyword
7. Language

Document type ^

<input type="checkbox"/> Article	68
<input type="checkbox"/> Conference paper	18
<input type="checkbox"/> Book chapter	8
<input type="checkbox"/> Review	4
<input type="checkbox"/> Note	1

Keyword ^

<input type="checkbox"/> Library Automation	35
<input type="checkbox"/> Library Services	31
<input type="checkbox"/> Libraries	19
<input type="checkbox"/> Automation	17
<input type="checkbox"/> Digital Libraries	15

Language ^

<input type="checkbox"/> English	92
<input type="checkbox"/> Chinese	2
<input type="checkbox"/> Croatian	2
<input type="checkbox"/> Indonesian	1
<input type="checkbox"/> Portuguese	1

Author name ^

<input type="checkbox"/> Mahanta, P.K.	4
<input type="checkbox"/> Ahammad, N.	2
<input type="checkbox"/> Barooah, P.K.	2
<input type="checkbox"/> De Sarkar, T.	2
<input type="checkbox"/> Hazarika, H.J.	2

[Show all](#)

Subject area ^

<input type="checkbox"/> Social Sciences	70
<input type="checkbox"/> Computer Science	32
<input type="checkbox"/> Arts and Humanities	24
<input type="checkbox"/> Engineering	13
<input type="checkbox"/> Decision Sciences	7

Range Individual

2018 – to >

Source title ^

<input type="checkbox"/> Library Philosophy and Practice	19
<input type="checkbox"/> Library Hi Tech News	8
<input type="checkbox"/> Journal of Indian Library Association	5
<input type="checkbox"/> Journal of Physics Conference Series	3
<input type="checkbox"/> Encyclopedia of Libraries Librarianship and Information Science First Edition Four Volume Set	2

2. Author search:

Select “Authors” On the homepage, at the top of the search bar, choose the “Authors” tab.

The screenshot shows the Scopus search interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with tabs: Documents, Authors (highlighted with a red box and an arrow), Researcher Discovery, Organizations, and Scopus AI (with a 'New' badge). Below the navigation bar, there is a search area with the text 'Start exploring'. Underneath, there are radio buttons for 'Search authors using: Author name (selected), ORCID, and Keyword'. There are three input fields: 'Enter last name *' (highlighted with a red border), 'Enter first name', and 'Enter affiliation name'. A blue 'Search' button is located at the bottom right of the search area. At the bottom of the page, there are links for 'Search History' and 'Saved Searches'.

Enter Author Name

Example:

- **Author Name:** A. Neelameghan.
- You may also add:
- **Affiliation** (optional):
- **ORCID ID** (optional, if known)
- Click **Search**.

The screenshot shows the Scopus search results page. The browser address bar displays the URL: <https://www.scopus.com/results/authorNamesList.uri?name=name&st1=Neelameghan&st2=A.&institute=&origin=searchauthorlookup>. The search criteria are: Author last name "Neelameghan", Author first name "A.". There is an 'Edit' link. On the left, there is a 'Refine results' section with a 'Limit to' button and an 'Exclude' button. Under 'Affiliation', there are three options: Addis Ababa University (1), Division of the General Information Programme (1), and Docum. Research and Training Center (1). On the right, there is a table of results. The table has columns: Author, Documents, Affiliation, City, and Country/Territory. The first result is: 1 Neelameghan, Arashanipalai Neelameghan, A. NEELAMEGHAN, A. 42 Sarada Ranganathan Endowment for Library Science Bangalore India. There is a 'View last title' link. At the bottom, there is a 'Display: 20 results per page' and a 'Top of page' link.

Author	Documents	Affiliation	City	Country/Territory
1 Neelameghan, Arashanipalai Neelameghan, A. NEELAMEGHAN, A.	42	Sarada Ranganathan Endowment for Library Science	Bangalore	India

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International cooperation in developing a digital library software and South Asia network

0 Citations

Library Science and Administration: Concepts, Methodologies, Tools, and Applications • Book
Chapter • 2017 • DOI: 10.4018/978-1-5225-3914-8.ch023

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This document is one of the chapters of a book series. [See all chapters](#)

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[Document](#) [Impact](#) [Cited by \(0\)](#) [References \(10\)](#) [Similar documents](#)

Abstract

Inter-country cooperation in any sector almost invariably begins with information exchange among the nations or

Abstract

Note: Author results differ many times, not the show exact result that I need.

3. Affiliation search:

Select “Affiliations” Tab:

On the homepage, click on “Affiliations”

Enter the Institution Name:

In the search box, type: Jadavpur University

Click on “Search.”

View the Affiliation Profile:

Scopus will display a list of institutions matching your search.

Select “Jadavpur University”

The screenshot shows the Scopus search interface. At the top, there is a search bar with the text 'Jadavpur University' entered. Below the search bar, there are tabs for 'Documents', 'Authors', 'Researcher Discovery', and 'Organizations'. The 'Organizations' tab is selected. Below the tabs, there is a search bar with the text 'Jadavpur University' entered. To the right of the search bar, there is a 'Search' button. Below the search bar, there is a 'Reset' button. Below the search bar, there is a 'Search tips' link. Below the search bar, there is a 'Search History' and 'Saved Searches' section. Below the search bar, there is a 'Combine queries' section. Below the search bar, there is a table of search results. The table has three columns: 'Query', 'Results', and 'Actions'. The first row shows the query 'AFFIL (jadavpur university)' with 39,892 results and a 'Set alert' button. The second row shows the query 'AFFIL (jadavpur university) AND (LIMIT-TO (AF-ID, "jadavpur university" 60020825))' with 39,855 results and a 'Set alert' button. The third row shows the query 'AFFIL (jadavpur university) AND (LIMIT-TO (AF-ID, "jadavpur university" 60020825))' with 39,855 results and a 'Set alert' button.

Query	Results	Actions
AFFIL (jadavpur university)	39,892 results	Set alert More
AFFIL (jadavpur university) AND (LIMIT-TO (AF-ID, "jadavpur university" 60020825))	39,855 results	Set alert More
AFFIL (jadavpur university) AND (LIMIT-TO (AF-ID, "jadavpur university" 60020825))	39,855 results	Set alert More

Nonhuman	2,385	Show abstract	View at Publisher	Related documents
<input type="checkbox"/> Controlled Study	2,263			
<input type="checkbox"/> Human	1,817			
<input type="checkbox"/> Unclassified Drug	1,786			
Show all				
Affiliation Clear (1)				
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Limited to Jadavpur University	39,855			
<input type="checkbox"/> University of Calcutta	1,529			
<input type="checkbox"/> Indian Statistical Institute, Kolkata	960			
<input type="checkbox"/> Indian Institute of Engineering Science and Technology, Shibpur	922			
<input type="checkbox"/> Indian Institute of Technology Kharagpur	828			
<input type="checkbox"/> Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science	675			
Show all				
Funding sponsor				
Country/territory				
Source type				

6	Article	Thermally activated delayed fluorescence-assisted thermosensing and thermochromic behaviors of bimetallic lanthanide(III) complexes based on heteroditopic phenanthroline-terpyridine ancillary ligand	Ahmed, T., Abedin, T., Baitalik, S.	Journal of Photochemistry and Photobiology A Chemistry, 472, 116749	2026	0
Show abstract View at Publisher Related documents						
7	Article	AIE-active naphthyl-hydrazine Schiff base chemosensor and its multi-ion sensing activities in the living cells	Ghosh, S., Paul, S., Halder, S., ... Maity, J., Sinha, C.	Spectrochimica Acta Part A Molecular and Biomolecular Spectroscopy, 346, 126909	2026	0
Show abstract View at Publisher Related documents						
8	Review	Recent advances in piezo-photo heterojunction: a review on dual catalytic function for wastewater remediation and simultaneous hydrogen generation.	Sau, A., Mondal, D., Roy, J., ... Biswas, D., Das, S.	Coordination Chemistry Reviews, 548, 217240	2026	0
Show abstract View at Publisher Related documents						
9	Article	Experimental investigation and numerical simulation of a growing crack in Alloy 617M under different test temperatures and thermal ageing conditions	Rakim, M., Acharyya, S.K., Dhar, S., Maitra, A.	Theoretical and Applied Fracture Mechanics, 141, 105217	2026	0
Show abstract View at Publisher Related documents						

4. Advanced search:

➤ Click on Advanced document search

The screenshot shows the Scopus search page. At the top, there is a search bar and navigation links. Below the search bar, there are tabs for 'Documents', 'Authors', 'Researcher Discovery', and 'Organizations'. A search query is entered in the 'Search documents' field. Below the search bar, there is a link for 'Advanced document search' which is highlighted with a red box and an arrow pointing to it. Below the search bar, there is a 'Search History' section showing several search queries and their results.

• **Boolean Operators search –**

➤ **AND** → Narrows your search

The screenshot shows the Scopus search page with the 'Advanced search' tab selected. The search query is entered in the 'Enter query string' field. Below the search bar, there is a 'Search History' section showing several search queries and their results. On the right side of the page, there is a 'Operators' section with a list of operators: AND, OR, AND NOT, PRE/, and W/. Below the operators, there is a 'Field codes' section with a list of field codes: Textual Content and Affiliations.

Scopus

Advanced query

"automation" AND "library services"

Save search | Set search alert | Edit in advanced search

Documents | Preprints | Secondary documents

2,113 documents found

Refine search

Search within results

Filters

Year

Range Individual

Document title	Authors	Source	Year	Citations
1 Article - Open access Sorting misorganized books in libraries based on ant colony algorithm	Chen, L.	Systems and Soft Computing, 7, 200372	2025	0
2 Review - Open access Network visualisation analysis of the transformative potential of generative AI tools in the education landscape	Govender, R., Ryankina, E., Boyasa, A., Harun, L.	Discover Education, 4(1), 426	2025	0

Feedback

OR → Broadens your search

Scopus

Advanced query

"digital libraries" OR "electronic libraries"

Save search | Set search alert | Edit in advanced search

Documents | Preprints | Secondary documents

290,040 documents found

Refine search

Search within results

Filters

Year

Range Individual

Document title	Authors	Source	Year	Citations
1 Article - Open access OcclusionNetPlusPlus: a multi-scale similarity network with adaptive occlusion detection for robust Iris recognition	Tanna, R., Patel, T., Alotaibi, F.M., Jhaveri, R.H., Gadokally, T.R.	International Journal of Cognitive Computing in Engineering, 7, pp. 74-85	2026	0
2 Article - Open access Bibliometric analysis of author count, funding, and citations in AI research	Lin, W.-C., Tsao, H.-H., Chen, Y.-S., Hsu, C.-L.	International Journal of Cognitive Computing in Engineering	2026	0

Feedback

NOT → Excludes terms from your search

Scopus

Advanced query

"library automation" NOT "school libraries"

Save search | Set search alert | Edit in advanced search

Documents | Preprints | Secondary documents

73 documents found

Refine search

Search within results

Filters

Year

Range Individual

Document title	Authors	Source	Year	Citations
1 Book Chapter Information sciences and sustainability	Holm, L.	Handbook on Information Sciences, pp. 342-358	2024	0
2 Book Chapter Libraries in Transformation: Navigating to AI-Powered Libraries	Messod, P., Minakhan, A.	Studies in Big Data, 157, pp. 1-428	2024	10

Feedback

Combined Boolean Example in Scopus Advanced Search

Advanced query: ((\"library automation\" OR \"ICT in libraries\") AND \"information services\" NOT \"school libraries\")

43 documents found

Document title	Authors	Source	Year	Citations
1 Book Chapter Information sciences and sustainability	Nolin, J.	Handbook on Information Sciences, pp. 342-358	2024	0
2 Book Chapter Libraries in Transformation: Navigating to AI-Powered Libraries	Meesad, P., Mingshwan, A.	Studies in Bio Data, 157, pp. 1-428	2024	10

Proximity Operator Example:

To find documents where the words *automation* and *library* appear close together, use the W/n operator (within *n* words):

Search your quarry - (automation W/3 library)

This retrieves documents where *automation* occurs within 3 words of *library* — e.g., “library automation system.”

Advanced query: (automation W/3 library)

5,624 documents found

Document title	Authors	Source	Year	Citations
1 Conference Paper The Convolution Computation Automatic Acceleration	Steinberg, B.Y., Baoliv, A.P., Bochkov, I.E., Sushko, A.N.	Lecture Notes in Computer Science , 16185 LNCS, pp. 76-90	2026	0
2 Article Systematic investigation on surrogate and active learning-based multivariate seismic fragility analysis under multiple sources of uncertainties	Yan, Y., Xie, Y., Xia, Y., Sun, L.	Reliability Engineering and System Safety , 265, 111588	2026	0

Reference:

1. Elsevier. (n.d.). *Scopus*. Retrieved November 4, 2025, from <https://www.scopus.com/home.uri?zone=header&origin=sbrowse>